

Analyzing the influence of driver, route and vehicle-related factors in Electric Vehicle energy consumption, based on real life data.

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Abstract—In electric vehicles context, battery consumption and "range anxiety" are the biggest worries. Different studies have shown that electric vehicle battery consumption depends on many factors and parameters that can be related with the vehicle, the driver or the route. In this paper we will show the impact of those parameters in the energy consumption based on a real life dataset. This dataset contains information about different real life routes completed by an electric vehicle (Volkswagen e-Golf). To see if a parameter affects the energy consumption, we will use different graphics and the statistical ANOVA-test and Welch's test. When parameters are categorical variables, we will see how the energy consumption changes between categories, showing that different values of that parameter implies different value of energy consumption. Continuous variables are going to be analyzed using the pairplot. The results show that using auxiliaries, an aggressive driving style and winter tires increase the consumption. Also, it is an important conclusion how in long routes the energy consumption is more stable than in shorter routes.

Index Terms—Electric vehicle, energy consumption, parameters.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, electric vehicle (EV) problems are related with energy consumption prediction accuracy, range limitation, lack of recharging stations... When planning a long route with an EV, many factors have to be taken into account, so it is important to have information about what parameters affect energy consumption in EVs. Also, energy recharging process is not very fast and the driver needs to wait for a while to recharge the EV.

There are many research works around the parameters that effect the energy consumption of an EV. Those parameters can be external parameters (route information, weather...), driver-related parameters (driving style, comfort) or vehicle-related parameters (battery capacity, tire type...). In this analysis we will compare different values of those parameters to see how they affect the energy consumption of an EV. To see the effect of all those parameters in the energy consumption, we will use

a dataset that is based on Spritmonitor [6] data. Spritmonitor is a web where users share their route information related with the energy consumption. Some users are EV car users so this study is done using one of the EV's data. The database is not available in Spritmonitor, but we use a database from Github [9], that takes the data from Spritmonitor.

In many research works, authors try to modelize those parameters mathematically, finding different equations that take into account the effect of that parameter in the energy consumption. In other research works, the analysis is focused on a few parameters and a deep analysis is made on that parameters. In this work, we consider a higher number of parameters and we try to show the effect of those parameters in the energy consumption, based on real life EV trips.

It is important to say that this analysis is a real life analysis, but all the trips are completed by the same user. This means that all the results are based on one EV, so the results may not be generalized for all the EVs.

The energy consumption of an EV is measured in kWh, but it is important to consider the distance of the route, because the energy consumption of a longer route in most of the cases will be higher. That is the reason to use the parameter kWh per 100km. Every EV has its own theoretical energy consumption per 100km (given by the EV manufacturer), but this value changes depending the parameters that we have mentioned before. Estimating an accurate value of the energy consumption per 100km for each route, taking into account the parameters that affect the energy consumption, is a difficult challenge.

Route information is an important factor to consider when we are trying to modelize the battery consumption. Route information takes into account many factors such as the elevation of the route, traffic of the route, type of the roads ... EV regenerate energy when we stop accelerating so it is clear that the elevation of a trip is an important factor.

Other parameters are related to the driver's behavior. Every

driver has its own driving style and depending on that style the energy consumption varies. In this dataset, the driver differentiated the trips in three categories and in each trip the conduction can be fast, moderate or normal.

The use of A/C and heating is also important for the analysis of energy consumption of an EV. When we use those comfort parameters, the EV has to send extra energy to those tasks and we will see how this affects the energy consumption.

In this study, we will start analyzing the continuous variables of the dataset and we will try to see the relation of those variables with the energy consumption per 100km. Those variables are the average speed, the total energy consumption and the trip distance.

Then, we will analyze the relation between the categorical variables and the energy consumption per 100km. Categorical variables are the ones that can take on one of a limited number of possible values. In our dataset, the categorical variables that we are going to consider are: driving style, A/C, park heating, tire type and road type. We will try to show that different values of those variables imply different energy consumption.

There are a lot of parameters that affect the energy consumption of an EV, so this means that when we are working with EVs, we have to consider many parameters if we want to make accurate predictions about the energy consumption.

II. RELATED WORK

Battery consumption estimation is one of the most important challenges in EV world to reduce the "range anxiety". Therefore, there are many research works around the parameters that effect energy consumption of a EV. Those parameters can be external parameters (route information, weather...), driver-related parameters (driving style, comfort) or vehicle-related parameters (battery capacity, tire type...).

Some works try to use the route information to create an algorithm that makes accurate energy consumption predictions [5]. If traffic is high, EVs have stronger accelerations and brakes and this directly affects the energy consumption. Reference [1] focuses its analysis in traffic influence and [3] studies the traffic influence among other parameters. This latter study also analyses the influence of the driver's behavior.

Wind intensity and wind direction also are important parameters to analyze. An EV will consume more battery if the wind is head on. Reference [4] studies the wind drag coefficient in road vehicles.

Other research works try to modelize the energy consumption of an electric vehicle. Reference [2] takes into account different variables such as braking strategy or auxiliary devices.

On the referenced research works, the data used is real life data and each work use different techniques. In [1], they use ANOVA test to compare the effect of traffic. In [5], as they try to make energy consumption predictions based on route information, they compare their model prediction and the measured values. In [3], they compare graphically the energy consumption depending on different values of weather, driving style or traffic.

In this study, we will include the effect of the tire type among other parameters. This effect is not analyzed in other research works and it is interesting to analyze it. This will show that in different periods of the year, the energy consumption can change due to the tire type, as the tire type can be winter tire or summer tire.

III. METODOLOGY

A. Dataset structure

The database of this study is composed of 3345 trips and for each trip there are 18 variables. The variables are of three types: vehicle-related variables, route-related variables and driver-related variables. The vehicle-related variables are the manufacturer, model, version, power (kW) of the vehicle and fuel type of the vehicle. The route-related variables are the following: trip distance, quantity (kWh), tire type, city, motor way, country roads, consumption (kWh/100km), avg. speed (km/h) and energy consumption rate deviation. The last one is the difference between the consumption of the vehicle in each trip and the theoretical vehicle energy consumption. Finally, the driver-related variables are A/C, park heating and driving style. A/C and park heating are driver-related variables because it is the driver who decides to use those extra parameters.

For this study, we only focus on the route-related variables and driver related variables, because vehicle-related variables are the same for all the trips, as we are considering only one EV. The goal of this study is to see the effect of different variables in the energy consumption, so the analysis is done comparing the different energy consumption for each category of the variable.

The dataset contains three rare trips, because there are three trips with the energy consumption above 50 kWh/100km and this is not possible. Theoretically, the energy consumption should be a number close to the division between the trip distance and the energy consumed in that distance, but this is not the case so those three trips are not considered in the study.

Three variables are related to the road type that is used in the trip. The different types of roads are city roads, country roads and motor ways. In each trip it is possible to use more than one road type and that is why there is not a single variable that indicates the road type. Those three variables are binary variables and are 1 if that type of road is used in the trip. When we compare the energy consumption per 100km with the road type in the study, we are considering trips that only use a single road type, otherwise, it is not possible to compare directly.

B. Variable analysis techniques

As we have mentioned before, in this study we will consider the route-related parameters and driver-related parameters. In order to evaluate the influence of the variables in the energy consumption, we divide route-related parameters and driver-related parameters into two big categories: continuous variables and categorical variables. To compare the continuous variables with the energy consumption per 100km, we use

the dispersion diagram. To see the effect of the categorical variables on the energy consumption per 100km, we use the box-plots. In some cases, we will compare continuous variables taking into account some categorical values. On those cases, we will use the dispersion diagram, differentiating each point as a different value of a parameter. To create those plots we have used Seaborn Python library [8].

In the box-plot graphics, it is easy to see the difference of energy consumption among the categories of a variable, but we use statistical ANOVA test and Welch's test to see that the effect of those variables are statistically significant. To use those tests, it is important to check some assumptions as homogeneity of variance, normality of the energy consumption per 100km and independence of observations. To check the homogeneity of variance, we have used the Levene test. When we try to see the independence of two categorical variables, we use the Chi-square test of independence. The significance level used in this work is 0.05. For this statistical analysis, we have used the Scipy Python library [7].

IV. RESULTS

A. Continuous variables

Firstly, we will see generally the effect of the continuous variables in the energy consumption. For that, we will use the pairs dispersion diagram.

Fig. 1. Pairplot

In Fig. 1 we can see how those continuous variables are related. It is interesting to see that there are three trips which are very long trips, above 1500km trips, and on those trips the total energy consumed is very high. However, the energy consumption per 100km is not high. Another important observation is how the trip distance affects the energy consumption

per 100km. In short trips, the energy consumption varies a lot but as the distance increases, the energy consumption is more constant. When the distance increases, the total energy consumed increases linearly, and the linear relation is very strong as the correlation number of those two variables is 0.96. The trip average speed is also important for the energy consumption per 100km. When the average speed is low, the energy consumption varies but as the average speed increases, the energy consumption starts getting stable around its mean value. We can see how the average speed vs energy consumption plot has funnel form. We will complete this analysis later on the work, analyzing different categories of different parameters.

It is also important to see the distribution of the energy consumption. The distribution of the energy consumption follows a normal distribution as it can be seen in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Histogram of energy consumption.

The distribution is asymmetric, as there are a few trips with an energy consumption above 25kWh/100km. As we said before, those values are related with the short trips. The normality of this variable is important for the ANOVA and Welch's test.

Now, let's see the effect of the categorical variables in the energy consumption.

B. Driving style

The variable driving style takes three values: fast, moderate and normal. 2331 trips are moderate, 912 are normal and 98 are fast.

In Fig. 3 we can see that the energy consumption is higher when the driving style is fast. The energy consumption takes the lowest values when the driving style is moderate. We can see that the driving style affects energy consumption and we can corroborate it with the ANOVA test. In this case, using the Levene test we see that the variance is equal in all the groups ($p=0.28$), so that is why we use the ANOVA test.

In Table I we can see how the p-value is lower than 0.05, so we can say driving style is statistically significant.

In Fig. 4 we see the relation of the average speed and the energy consumption, indicating the driving style for each trip. As we can see, when the style is fast, almost all the trips are

Fig. 3. Driving style

TABLE I
ANOVA TABLE

	<i>Sum sq</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Driving style	1442.27	2	50.26	3.11e-22
Residuals	47890.87	3338		

above the average consumption. Higher average speed doesn't mean a higher energy consumption because the highest values of the energy consumption are in the slowest trips.

In Table II we can see the contingency table of driving style and road type. In this contingency table we can see that fast driving style mostly happens in motor ways. We can use the Chi squared test to see if those variables are independent or not. The p-value is $7.31e-7$ and this means that the dependence of those variables is statistically significant.

TABLE II
CONTINGENCY TABLE

	<i>City</i>	<i>Country road</i>	<i>Motor way</i>
Fast	12	4	34
Moderate	361	97	550
Normal	183	50	147

Fig. 4. Relation of speed and driving style.

C. Tire type

Tire type takes two possible values: winter tires or summer tires. In the dataset there are 1824 trips with summer tires and 1517 with winter tires.

Fig. 5. Tire type

In Fig. 5 we can see the difference between using winter tires or summer tires. As it can be appreciated, the use of winter tires implies a higher energy consumption. In this case, the variance is not equal in both groups ($p=2.34e-6$) so we used the Welch's t-test. P-value is $1.44e-65$ and that means the tire type is statistically significant.

D. Air conditioning (A/C)

As we told in the introduction, some of the parameters that affect the energy consumption are related with the comfort of the trip and air conditioning is one of them. It is supposed that when we use the A/C the EV requires more energy so consumption is higher. The following box-plot confirms that.

Fig. 6. A/C

In this case, the variance is not equal in all the groups, as the Levene test p-value is $5.4e-9$, so again, we will use the Welch's t-test to see if the difference of both groups is significant. The p-value we get is $2.4e-14$ so we can say the use of A/C is statistically significant.

E. Park heating

Another parameter which is related with the comfort of the trip is the heating. Again, it is supposed that when we use the heating the EV is going to consume more. Fig. 7 corroborates that.

Fig. 7. Park heating

In the box-plot it is clear that variance in group 1 is smaller. Levene's test p-value is $2.26e-25$, so variance is not equal in both groups. Using the Welch's t-test to see if the difference in both groups is significant, the p-value we get is $2.4e-14$ so we can say using heating is statistically significant.

F. Road type

Road type is divided in three variables in the dataset. In each trip is possible to use more than one type of road so it is not possible to use a unique variable to assign the road type.

To solve this problem, we consider only the trips that use a single road type. There are 731 trips that only use motor way, 556 that only use city roads and 152 trips that only use country roads. This way, we can compare those trips directly and see if the road type affects the energy consumption.

Fig. 8. Road type

In this box-plot we can see how country road trips are the ones with the highest energy consumption. It is important to see how the energy consumption varies in city trips. Even though the average value for the motor way trips and city

trips is very similar, the standard deviation is much higher in city trips. These differences can be seen in the Table III.

TABLE III
ANOVA TABLE

Category	Median	Average	Standar deviation
City	13.75	14.32	3.91
Country roads	15.20	15.06	2.21
Motor way	13.60	13.84	2.04

As we can see, energy consumption is higher in country roads and the standard deviation is not that high.

G. Road type, average speed and trip distance relation

To understand what is happening, it is interesting to see how the distance of the trip and the road type are related.

Fig. 9. Relation of distance and road type.

In Fig. 9 we can see that in short trips the energy consumption varies a lot, and this is directly related to the road type. In general, the shortest trips are city trips and that is why the variation of the energy consumption is so high in city roads. Also, as the trip distance is getting higher, we can see how the energy consumption starts being more stable. In Fig. 9 we can also see clearly the three trips over 1500km. In those long trips, the energy consumption was stable around the average value of the energy consumption.

At the beginning of this section we have analyzed the continuous variables and we have seen that when average speed increases the energy consumption starts being stable.

In Fig. 10 we can see again how the average speed and the energy consumption are related, but now we can identify the road type of each trip. We can see how the slowest trips are city trips and the fastest ones are motor way trips. Country road trips are faster than city trips and slower than country road trips. Again, we can see that the deviation of slowest trips is very high.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this study we have seen the effect of different parameters in the energy consumption of an EV based on a public dataset of real-life journeys. As expected, all the parameters that we have mentioned affect the energy consumption. The results

Fig. 10. Relation of average speed and road type.

were not only considered graphically, but also we have used statistical tests like ANOVA and Welch's test to support the results.

In this analysis we use statistical techniques to get stronger results. Although in the box-plots we see clearly the difference between one category to other in the energy consumption of an EV, statistical analysis gives a more detailed analysis and a stronger information.

Driving style is an important parameter to consider when we are studying energy consumption of an EV. We have seen that a fast style indicates a higher energy consumption. Driving style is related with the road type, and we have seen that most of the fast style trips were in motor ways.

Energy consumption varies a lot in short trips and short trips are directly related with the city trips. Even that in average the energy consumption is not very different in cities and motor ways, the variation of energy consumption in city trips indicates that in short trips it is difficult to predict the energy consumption. This may be due to the hard accelerations and breaking that happen in short trips or due to the interrupted traffic that happen many times in cities.

Comfort-related parameters increase the energy consumption. The results show how the use of A/C and park heating increase the energy consumption. Also, tire type is important and tire type is directly related with the time of the year. The analysis show that winter tires consume more energy than summer tires.

Driving style is the parameter that affects the most the energy consumption according to this dataset. This can be seen in the difference of energy consumption between a fast driving style and a moderate driving style.

When we are planning a route with an EV, it is important to consider all those factors that affect the energy consumption. In short trips, range anxiety is not a big problem but in longer trips, it is important to know whether we need to recharge the battery or not and those parameters help us anticipating that problem.

In works related to modeling electric vehicle energy consumption, those parameters should be included in the model because they give a lot of information of the energy consump-

tion behavior in different scenarios.

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